

INTERPRETATION OF LINGUISTIC OPPOSITION AND RESEARCH
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Abstract: Linguistic opposition is one of the most important topics of modern linguistics. This term is one of the important categories of cognitive linguistics. This article presents some reflections on the role of opposition in linguistics.

Keywords: opposition, anthropocentric approach, independent paradigm, concept, cognitive term, linguoculturology, neutral attitude.

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Today, the phenomenon of homonymy has been studied and is being studied by various researchers. Also, the phenomenon of homonymy has been thoroughly studied in almost all languages of the world. In particular, Sh.Rakhmatullaev, M.Ravshanov, B.Suyunov, M.Joraboyeva, U.Tursunov, N.Rajabov, M.Mirtojdiyev, K.Usmanov carried out scientific research on the phenomenon of homonymy in Uzbek linguistics and its comparison with different language units. In the conducted studies, the phenomenon of homonymy is present in an adjective, a word, a phrase, a figurative expression, a phrase, a sentence, or even a sign (punctuation mark) to affix homonymy, lexical homonymy, phrasal homonymy, paraphasic homonymy, phraseological homonymy, gaponymy, and symbolic homonymy, etc. is divided. It can be seen that the phenomenon of homonymy exists both in lexical units and in grammatical units.

Mahmud Koshghari is the first researcher of Turkish homonyms. Koshghari not only collected materials related to homonyms, but also scientifically interpreted them. For example, in the work "Devonu lug'otit turk" he showed that the word "grass" is used in four different meanings, such as plant, dry hay, medicine and poison. Later, this word was enriched with meanings such as fire, the core of the word to pass. According to historical data, the word fire, meaning fire, comes from a completely different root. Mahmud Koshghari shows this word in its middle form. This is also confirmed by Alisher Navoi's works: The world is like the sun, it is time to celebrate, it is time to celebrate the world.

In our opinion, there is sufficient reason for this opinion. Because the word "to burn", which is in active use today, also means to burn, to burn:

O'rtamoq I. To take grass; to burn, to burn Our houses were on fire, warmed by the heat... T. Tola. People... red soldiers destroyed our Lady... N. Safarov.

O'rtamoq II. portable. Finally heat up; to burn A flood of fire from the sun cuts through the crowded city streets. J. Abdullakhanov. Oriyat.

O'rtamoq III portable. To cause mental anguish; to burn To touch the heart. To take care of life. Why don't you keep silent, cry, cry with your heart. E. Rahim. Shoot a hundred times below you, cut the enemy in half. "Alpomish". When the trumpet sounds in Akrom's ear, his dream that will never be fulfilled becomes painful and cuts his body. E. Usmanov.

Revealing the semantic and poetic properties of homonyms in his works, Navoi considers them the wealth of his native language and emphasizes that the Turkish (Uzbek) language is extremely rich in homonyms and it is possible to create beautiful expressions based on them:

"The word ``horse" has one meaning: pain, another meaning: "markab" and another meaning: command to throw a stone or an arrow. I'm called mundok in this tajnis.

Go fast, begum. My dear, my dear, run away from everything.

And these two stanzas, full of rhyme, are characteristic of the Turkish language, so they say that there is no such thing and it has a muni feeling...".

The research of historical homonymy in Turkic languages, including Uzbek, is the object of a separate work conducted in the diachronic aspect. Some aspects of this problem were partially analyzed in the works of S.Mutallibov.

Homonyms are used in written monuments in the same way as they are used in modern Turkic languages for various stylistic purposes. However, the use of homonyms in the language of written monuments is much more limited compared to the present. It should not be concluded that such homonyms are a linguistic phenomenon of the later period. Homonyms present in the vocabulary of modern Turkic languages were also reflected in ancient times, but were used in a limited way in the language of written monuments: балик I "балик", балик II "шахар"; бар I "бор, мавжуд", бар- I "бормоқ", адін I "бошқа", адін- I "ўзгартирмоқ, тўғирламоқ", ағір I "оғир", ағір I "хурматли, қадрли", ай I "ой", ай II "ой, вақт", ар- I "бўлмоқ", ар- I "алдамоқ". Therefore, the use of homonyms in the ancient Turkic language indicates the diversity of the lexical layer of that language.

M. Ravshanov writes in his candidacy thesis on "Homonyms in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language" as follows: "Until now, in the linguistics of our country, there were two opposite points of view, two different approaches to the study of homonymy and polysemy. According to the first (traditional) point of view, words that are phonetically the same, genetically unrelated and only compatible with each other during the historical development

of the language are considered homonyms. The remaining cases, that is, when lexemes with different meanings remain materially the same, are considered ambiguous. Supporters of the more widespread second point of view believe that in addition to real (heterogeneous) homonyms, there are also semantic (homogeneous) homonyms, words that were initially one word, and then arose as a result of breaking the semantic link. Such a point of view O.S. Akhmanova, R.A. Budagov, V.V. Vinogradov, Y.M. Galkina, N.P. Kolesnikova, L.A. Novikov, S.I. Ojegov, A.A. Reformasky, A. It is also given in the studies of I.Smirnisky, I.I.Fomina, A.Y.Shaykevich, N.M.Shansky, D.N.Shmelyov and others." In particular, I. Vardul considers the concept of homonym to be applicable to all units of the linguistic system - "from the morpheme at the morphological level, to the sentence and period at the syntactic level, and to the message at the supra-syntactic level."

Scientist Y. Maslov, who studied the phenomenon of homonymy, writes: "In the theory of language, it seems more effective to derive from a much wider understanding of homonymy and homonym than in the practice of lexicographic work. By homonymy we mean the same pronunciation of two different signifiers. On the one hand, this refers to understanding at the level of words, morphemes or morpheme units, and phrases. Different divisions can be distinguished within the concept defined in the manner shown.

Above, according to Y. Maslov, homonyms are two different signifiers, i.e. the same pronunciation of the signifier. However, homonyms are words that are pronounced the same with two different meanings. It is the use of homonyms that determines the uniqueness of the speech.

G. Ismailov in his article on homonyms: "It is known that homonymy is a lexical phenomenon based on the same structure, but not related to each other in terms of meaning. Homonymy plays an important role in the emergence of interaction between lexemes in different languages, and also in Uzbek.

E.V. Sevortyan thinks about homonyms as verb-type stems, Kyrgyz scholar B.O. Oruzbayeva says that one-stem homonyms are one of the ancient ways of forming words in Turkic languages, and a number of other scholars consider homonyms as the word of one word family of another word. the result of transition to the category is called conversion.

It is important to look at the history of homonymy and related linguistic phenomena, to evaluate existing theoretical conclusions, to express our own attitudes. Studying it and applying it to the public will lead to an increase in language richness. That is why it is important to learn homonymy today.

Russian linguists have done a lot of work on homonymy. In the 60s of the last century, Academician V. V. Vinogradov emphasized that linguists are giving

special importance to the issue of homonymy, and that they are trying to study this issue in connection with general issues such as the word and its phonological, morphematic construction, typology, forms of formation, morphonology and syntagmatics. was

The fact that homonymy is characteristic of morphological units is not new for today. Because L.A. Bulakhovsky put forward the same idea in his article "Iz jizni omonimov" published in 1928. The author tried to distinguish different types of homonyms, divided them into lexical, morphological, same and different morphological groups, described them in the form of basic and artificial, close and non-close concepts.

Homonyms are words that do not have common meaning elements, are not conceptually connected, but are written and pronounced the same. The presence of such words in the language and related phenomena are called homonymy. Homonymy is a phenomenon widely used in works of art, in the process of everyday communication, and its presence significantly contributes to making speech effective. Homonyms enrich the language by being used in classical literature in the creation of tajnis, ihyom art and tuyuq genre, and in askiya payrovs as puns and puns.

In conclusion, analyzing the phenomenon of homonymy and homonyms as a whole, determining their place in the literary text is one of the urgent problems of linguistics.

REFERENCE:

1. Mahmudov N. Tilning mukammal tadqiqi yo'llarini izlab// O'zbek tili va adabiyoti T.:2012, 3-16-B;
2. Вардуть И.Ф. Место семантики в лингвистическом описании// Вкн.: Проблемы семантики. – М.: Наука, 1974. –С.17-18;
3. Г.М. Омонимия транс терминов (на материале узбекского языка) Институт языка и литературы Академии наук Республики Узбекистан. 2012.– С.67;
4. Маслов Ю.С. Омонимы в словарях и омонимия в языке (к постановке вопроса) // Вопросы теории и истории языка: Сборник в честь профессора Б. А. Ларина. – Л.: Изд-во Ленинградского ун-та, 1963. –С.128-202;
5. Орузбаева Б.О. Словообразование в киргизском языке. – Фрунзе: 1955. С-262
18. Равшанов М. Омонимы в толковом словаре узбекского языка; Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук. – Тошкент, 1991. – С.5;
6. Смирнитский А.И. Лексикология английского языка. –Москва:1956. С-160-161;

7. Rajabov F. Omonimiya. – Toshkent: Yangi kitob nashriyoti, 2019. – 264 b;
8. Azimjon Latifjon oqli Melikuziev. (2022). HISTORICAL AND MODERN CLASSIFICATION OF PARALINGUISTICS. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(10), 126–128. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/UAH57>
9. Khakimov, M. K., & oqli Melikuziev, A. L. (2022). The History of Paralinguistic Researches. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 13, 90-95.
10. oqli Melikuziev, A. L. (2022). HISTORICAL AND MODERN CLASSIFICATION OF PARALINGUISTICS. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(10), 126-128.
11. Mukhammad, K. K., & oqli Melikuziev, A. L. (2022, December). THE ESSENCE OF NONVERBAL COMMUNICATION. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES* (Vol. 1, No. 19, pp. 91-93).